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A Quasi Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding Preconception Care among Married Women in Selected Community of Amritsar, Punjab

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For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>**Harleen Kaur**Assistant Professor
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Amritsar, Punjab, India**Abstract**

Improving preconception health can result in improved reproductive health outcomes, with potential for reducing societal costs as well. Preconception care aims to promote the health of women of reproductive age before conception and thereby improve pregnancy-related outcomes. To improve pregnancy outcomes, including low birth weight, premature birth, and infant mortality has slowed, in part, because of inconsistent delivery and implementation of interventions before pregnancy to detect, treat, and help women modify behaviours, health conditions, and risk factors that contribute to adverse maternal and infant outcomes. There are several interventions that, if implemented before pregnancy, can improve pregnancy outcomes for women and infants. However, millions of women and couples do not receive such interventions and services

The present study was undertaken by the investigator to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding preconception care among married women. The study sample was married women and accessible population was married women residing in selected community of Amritsar, Punjab. A sample of 60 married women (30 in experimental group and 30 in control group) was taken under study. Analysis and the interpretation were done in accordance with the objective lay down for the study.

The study findings revealed that · In experimental group, according to pre-test knowledge, majority (90%) of married women had average followed by (10%) below average knowledge score In control group, according to pre-test knowledge, majority (93.3%) of married women had average followed by (6.7%) below average knowledge score.

1. In experimental group, post-test knowledge score (43.3%) had good and (56.7%) had average knowledge score and post-test knowledge score (73.3%) had average followed by (26.7%) below average knowledge score.
2. According to the comparison of mean difference between pre- test and post-test knowledge score in experimental group was found statistically significant with 't' value 10.851 whereas comparison of mean difference between pre- test and post-test knowledge score in control group was found statistically non-significant with 't' value -1.034 at $p < 0.05$. Hence hypothesis H₀ and H₁ accepted at $p < 0.05$
3. No significant association of pre-test knowledge was found with Age in years, Type of family, Place of residence, Qualification, Source of information, Gravida at $p < 0.05$. Significant association of post-test knowledge was found with source of information at $p < 0.05$.
4. Hence It can be concluded that structured teaching program was effective in improving knowledge among married women regarding preconception care. Key words: comparison, knowledge, antenatal women

Keywords Effectiveness, Structured teaching program, Knowledge, Preconception care, Married woman

Introduction "There is such a special sweetness in being able to participate in creation."
- Pamela S. Nadav

Improving preconception health can result in improved reproductive health outcomes, with potential for reducing societal costs as well. Preconception care aims to promote the health of women of reproductive age before conception and thereby improve pregnancy-related outcomes. To improve pregnancy outcomes, including low birth weight, premature birth, and infant mortality has slowed, in part, because of inconsistent delivery and implementation of interventions before pregnancy to detect, treat, and help women modify behaviors, health conditions, and risk factors that contribute to adverse maternal and infant outcomes. There are several interventions that, if implemented before pregnancy, can improve pregnancy outcomes for women and infants. However, millions of women and couples do not receive such interventions and services.

Steel et al (2015)¹Preconception care has received increased attention due to growing evidence that maternal health prior to conception can directly affect the health of the mother and the fetal environment during pregnancy. The majority of research attention over the last 20 years has been directed to the benefits of folic acid supplementation in preventing birth defects. The broader field of preconception care research emphasizes the impact of the fetal environment on adverse outcomes such as miscarriage, stillbirth, congenital disorders, and macrosomia. Fetal environment has also been found to impact on risk of the development of chronic diseases such as obesity, diabetes and cardiovascular disease and cancer through epigenetic and other cellular responses to developmental exposures. Maternal health behaviours which have been clearly identified as important in the context of preconception care include diet, smoking, alcohol consumption and exposure to communicable diseases.

Objective of study

1. To assess the pre-test knowledge score of experimental and control group regarding preconception care among married women.
2. To assess the post-test knowledge score of experimental and control group regarding preconception care among married women.
3. To compare the pre-test and post-test knowledge score of experimental and control group regarding preconception care among married women.
4. To find out association of knowledge with selected socio-demographic variables such as Age in years, Type of family, Place of residence, Qualification, Source of information, Gravida.

Objective 1: To assess the pre-test knowledge score of experimental and control group regarding preconception care among married women. In experimental group, according to pre-test knowledge, majority (90%) of married women had average followed by (10%) below average knowledge score. In control group, according to pre-test knowledge, majority (93.3%) of married women had average followed by (6.7%) below average knowledge score.

Objective 2: To assess the post-test knowledge score of experimental and control group regarding preconception care among married women.

In experimental group, as per post-test knowledge score (43.3%) had good and (56.7%) had average knowledge score and as per post-test knowledge score (73.3%) had average followed by (26.7%) below average knowledge score.

Objective 3: To compare the pre-test and post-test knowledge score of experimental and control group regarding preconception care among married women.

According to the comparison of mean difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge score in experimental group was found statistically significant with 't' value 10.851 whereas comparison of mean difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge score in control group was found statistically non significant with 't' value -1.034 at $p < 0.05$. Hence hypothesis H₀ and H₁ accepted at $p < 0.05$

Objective 4: To find out association of knowledge with selected socio-demographic variables such as Age in years, Type of family, Place of residence, Qualification, Source of information, Gravida.

No significant association of pre-test knowledge was found with Age in years, Type of family, Place of residence, Qualification, Source of information, Gravida at $p < 0.05$. Significant association of post-test knowledge was found with source of information at $p < 0.05$.

Review of Literature

A good research does not exist in a vacuum. Review of literature is an essential step in the development of a research project. It helps the researcher to design the proposed study in a scientific manner. So as to achieved the desired result. For each finding to be meaningful should be an existence of previous knowledge.

Review of literature helps the investigator to develop insight in the problem and gain information about the problem and what has been done before. It provides basis for future investigation, justifies the need for replication, throws light on the feasibility of the study, constraints of data collection and relates the finding from one study to another with a hope to establish a comprehensive body of scientific knowledge and a professional discipline from which valid and pertinent theories may be developed.

Based on the objectives of the study, the literature from various sources had been reviewed and arranged under following headings:

Section-I: Studies related to preconception care.

Section-II: Studies related to knowledge and attitude regarding preconception care.

Section-III: Studies related to effectiveness of structured teaching programme

Section-I: Studies related to preconception care Paulik E et.al.(2009)35A study was conducted in Hungary, to determine demographic, obstetric and pregnancy care related factors of folic acid intake during preconceptional and prenatal period of pregnancy. A Questionnaire-based retrospective study was conducted in 349 pregnant women. The results showed that taking folic acid during pregnancy increased with age, and decreased with gestational age. Prenatal folic acid intake significantly related to the earlier intake of folic acid, and prenatal multivitamin medication. So the researcher concluded that it is important to target women who are less likely to take preconceptional folic acid as well as to increase awareness of women of childbearing age in general through an intensive campaign and improved education.

Renee B et.al.(2008)[36] A study was conducted in USA, to investigate the intersection of women's pregnancy planning beliefs with preconception care barriers among African American women and explored its connection to preconception experiences. Certain questionnaire was used in African American women (n = 168) recruited from health department sites. Results showed that these women are unfamiliar with preconception care and failed in planning of pregnancy. So the nurses should apply their understanding of the bio psychosocial dimensions of health in support of the goals of preconception healthcare.

Keith A.et .al(2006)[38] A survey study was conducted in Arizona, to evaluate the women knowledge level and beliefs about preconception healthcare among 499 women. The results indicated that all women in the study (98.6%) realized the importance of optimizing their health prior to a pregnancy, only 39% could ever recall their physician discussing preconception health. The majority of the women in this study population who were interested in preconception health education preferred the information prior to a pregnancy (74.8%) or at the time of their annual medical exam (11.9%)

WHO (2013)[2] report shows that preconception care has a positive impact on maternal and child health outcomes. Addressed primarily at health professionals responsible for developing national and local health policies, the report provides a foundation for implementing a package of promotive, preventive and curative health interventions shown to have been effective in improving maternal and child health. A wide range of sectors and stakeholders needs to be engaged to ensure universal access to preconception care. The report also guides non-health sectors, foundations and civil society organizations to collaborate with, and support, public health policy-makers to maximize gains for maternal and child health through preconception care.

WHO (2013)[3] Preconception care is the provision of biomedical, behavioural and social health interventions to women and couples before conception occurs. It aims at improving their health status, and reducing behaviours and individual and environmental factors that contribute to poor maternal and child health outcomes. Its ultimate aim is to improve maternal and child health, in both the short and long term.

PCHHC (2013)[4] The Consumer Workgroup of the PCHHC launched Show Your Love (SYL), a national campaign designed to improve the health of young men and women to promote optimal preconception health and reproductive life planning. Since then, the campaign has expanded and diversified to better help young adults find resources to lead healthy lifestyles and achieve their goals. Show Your Love is a new consumer resource centre and consumer social media campaign that encourages women and men to show love to themselves, their partners, their friends, and future children by taking steps towards a healthier lifestyle and wellbeing.

Pregnancy Quick Start[18] Starting to plan for the pregnancy is an early planning process, which main goal is to decide the proper moment to get pregnant and then the medical care for both the baby and the mother, and modifying whatever is needed to create a healthy environment by preventing stress, nutrients deficiency, birth defects or any other pregnancy problem. With so many women getting pregnant every year just wanting motherhood without planning. In fact, it is estimated that 40% of pregnancies in the United States are not planned, but those women who have a pregnancy plan

undoubtedly improve their chance of living smoothly through their pregnancies and giving birth to healthy babies.

Methodology A quasi experimental study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding preconception care among married women in selected community of Amritsar, punjab.

Purpose of The Study

The purpose of study is to enhance knowledge of married women regarding pre-conception by means of Structured Teaching Programme so as to reduce the incidence of maternal mortality and morbidity, prenatal mortality and to decrease congenital malformation

The methodology is the most important part of the research as it is framework for conducting a study. Research methodology defines what the activity of research is and how to proceed and how to measure progress. It indicates the general pattern for organizing the procedure to gather valid and reliable data for an investigation. This chapter deals with methodology adopted for present research statement "A quasi experimental study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding preconception care among married women in selected community of Amritsar, Punjab."

Research Approach

Research approach involves the description of plan to investigate the phenomenon under study. Therefore approach helps to decide about the presence or absence as well as manipulation and control over variable.⁵⁰

For the present study, the Quantitative research approach was considered appropriate as it aimed to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding preconception care among married women in selected community of Amritsar, Punjab."

Research Design

Research design is the researcher's overall plan for answering the research questions or testing the research hypothesis.⁵⁰

For the present study, Quasi-experimental (Non-equivalent pre-test post-test control group design) was utilized to achieve the objectives of study and is shown in figure 2.

Experimental group O1 X O2

Control group O1 O2

Research Setting

Research setting is defined as physical, social and cultural site in which researcher conduct the study.^[50]

The present study was conducted in selected community Amritsar, Punjab.

Population

Population is the entire aggregation of cases that meets a designated set of criteria for researcher.^[51]

The target population for present study was married women and accessible population was married women residing in selected community of Amritsar, Punjab.

Sampling

A sample is a selected proportion of the defined population.⁵⁰ The total sample was 60 married women from selected community of Amritsar, Punjab and purposive sampling technique was used for study.

Statistics Used in the Study

Variables under Study

Variables are defined as attribute of a person that varies, that is, taken on different values.

Dependent variable- Variables that change as the independent variable is manipulated by the researcher. For the present study knowledge of married women regarding preconception care was dependent variable.

Independent variable- Variables that are purposely manipulated or changed by the researcher. For the present study Structured Teaching Programme was independent variable.

Socio-demographic variables- The characteristics and attributes of the study subjects

are considered demographic variable. For the present study demographic variable were Age in years, type of family, Place of residence, Qualification, Source of information, Gravida.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria:

Married women who were willing to participate in study.

Married women who were present at the time of the study.

Married women whose last menstrual periods were not missed.

Exclusion criteria:

Married women who were not willing to participate in study.

Married women who were not present at the time of the study. Married women whose last menstrual periods were missed.

Selection and Development of Tool

As the present study is to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding preconception care among married women in selected community of Amritsar, Punjab. A structured questionnaire regarding preconception care will be developed to assess the knowledge on preconception care among selected women.

The research tool was selected and developed by keeping in mind the objectives of study, by reviewing theoretical sources, previous studies, and internet and through discussion with field experts.

Description of Tool

The tool consists of the following parts:

Part A: Socio-demographic profile

This part included items for obtaining personal information about married women such as Age in years, Type of family, Place of residence, Qualification, Source of information, Gravida.

Part B: Structured questionnaire regarding preconception care.

It was prepared by the researcher and was contain items to assess knowledge of married women regarding preconception care. This part consists of multiple choice questions on preconception care. Each correct response was given one mark and wrong response was given 0.

Criterion Measures

Knowledge of married women regarding preconception can be categorized into three levels:

Level of Knowledge Percentage Score

Good > 80% > 22

Average 40-80% 11-22

Below Average < 40% < 11

Maximum score: 28

Minimum score: 0

Validity of Tool

Validity of the tool refers to the adequacy of the domain being studied. Content validity of the tool was confirmed by expert's opinion regarding the relevance of the item. Content validity concerns the degree to which an instrument has an appropriate sample of items for the construct being measured and adequately covers the construct. The self structured tool consisting of questions on knowledge regarding preconception care circulated among experts of various field of specialisation. Their valuable suggestions were obtained and incorporated. The final tool was consisted of 2 parts after necessary changes done. The structured questionnaire was finalized with 28 items.

Reliability of Tool

The reliability is the degree of consistency and accuracy with which an instrument measures the attribute for which it is designed to measure.⁵⁰ Reliability of the tool was computed by split half technique and was calculated by Spearman's Brown Correlation Coefficient formula and reliability of the tool was $r = 0.86$. Hence, the tool was reliable

Pilot Study

A pilot study is a miniature of actual study in which the instruments are administered to the subjects drawn from the same population. The purpose is to find out the feasibility of study.⁵¹ The pilot study was conducted in the month of December 2016 to ensure the reliability of tool and feasibility of the study and the sample was consisted of 12 subjects (6 experimental and 6 in control group). During pilot study it was found that structured teaching programme was effective in improving the knowledge regarding preconception care among married women.

Data Collection Procedure

Data collection was done from February 2017 to march 2017. Data collected from 60 married women in selected community of Amritsar by purposive sampling technique. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authorities of the selected community before approaching subjects. The structured questionnaire was edited by the experts .Prior to collecting data , investigator gave self-introduction to the subjects and explaining the purpose of gathering information; a good rapport was established with the subjects. They were assured that their responses will be kept confidential and the information will be used only for research purpose. Verbal consent was taken from subjects. On first day, pre-test was taken from the subjects of experimental group and researcher delivered the structured teaching programme to them on the same day. The post test of experimental group will be conducted on 4th day of pre-test. Similarly, pre-test and post- test was conducted on control group but no structured teaching programme was be given to them.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to the data collection procedure, formal permission was obtained from the concerned authorities of the selected community of Amritsar, Punjab and verbal consent was taken from subjects who were under study. To gain their confidence, they were told that their responses would be used only for research purpose. They were also informed about their right to refuse from participating in the study. Subjects who were willing to participate were included in the study.

Analysis

Analysis of the data was done in accordance with objectives of the study. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 16.0 software. Descriptive statistics was used for calculating percentage, mean, standard deviation (SD) and Inferential statistics i.e. chi square and t-test were used to assess knowledge score in association with demographic variables as per research objectives. Pie charts and bar diagrams were used to depict the findings of the study.

This paper dealt with the research approach, research design, research setting, population, sample and sampling technique, variables under study, inclusion and exclusion criteria, selection and development of tool, description of tool, validity of tool, reliability of tool, pilot study, data collection procedure, ethical consideration, and plan for analysis.

This paper dealt with analysis and interpretation of data collected from 60 married women regarding preconception care. Major findings of the study were discussed according to objectives. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis i.e. frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, chi-square, t-test. The finding of the study was depicted through the use of frequency distribution tables, bar diagrams and pie- charts.

Sample characteristics

1. According to the age in years, (46.7%) of married women, in experimental group and almost half (50%) of married women, in control group were in the age group (23-27) years.
2. According to type of family, majority (70%) of married women of experimental group and (53.3%) of control group were belonging to nuclear family.
3. According to place of residence, majority (60%) of married women of experimental group and (53.3%) of control group were lived in urban community.
4. According to qualification, majority (60%) of married women of experimental group were having secondary qualification level and (46.7%) of control group were having metric qualification level.
5. According to source of information, majority (60%) of married women of experimental group and (50%) of control group had gained knowledge from family members/friends.
6. According to gravida majority (83.3%) of married women of experimental group and (93.3%) of control group were nulligravida.

Findings

1. According to the age (in years), (46.7%) of married women, in experimental group and almost half (50%) of married women, in control group were in the age group (23-27) years.
2. According to type of family, majority (70%) of married women of experimental group and (53.3%) of control group were belonging to nuclear family.
3. According to place of residence, majority (60%) of married women of experimental group and (53.3%) of control group were lived in urban community.

4. According to qualification, majority (60%) of married women of experimental group were having secondary qualification level and (46.7%) of control group were having metric qualification level.
5. According to source of information, majority (60%) of married women of experimental group and (50%) of control group had gained knowledge from family members/friends.
6. According to gravid majority (83.3%) of married women of experimental group and (93.3%) of control group were nulligravida.
7. In experimental group, according to pre-test knowledge, majority (90%) of married women had average followed by (10%) below average knowledge score In control group, according to pre-test knowledge, majority (93.3%) of married women had average followed by (6.7%) below average knowledge score.
8. In experimental group, post-test knowledge score (43.3%) had good and (56.7%) had average knowledge score and post-test knowledge score (73.3%) had average followed by (26.7%) below average knowledge score.
9. According to the comparison of mean difference between pre- test and post test knowledge score in experimental group was found statistically significant with 't' value 10.851 whereas comparison of mean difference between pre- test and post test knowledge score in control group was found statistically non significant with 't' value -1.034 at $p < 0.05$. Hence hypothesis H_0 and H_1 accepted at $p < 0.05$
10. No significant association of pre-test knowledge was found with Age in years, Type of family, Place of residence, Qualification, Source of information, Gravida at $p < 0.05$. Significant association of post-test knowledge was found with source of information at $p < 0.05$.

Conclusion Preconception care is a prevention strategy that helps women to prepare for pregnancy by improving their health prior to conception. It includes health practices related to safeguarding fertility, preparing for pregnancy, and identifying and addressing risk factors. It also enhances pregnancy outcomes by optimizing health in the critical first weeks of pregnancy, before many women know they are pregnant. Preconception health strategies encourage men and women to actively plan their pregnancy, seek out health information and advice, and to make health changes prior to conception. Studies have shown the importance of teaching program is beneficial to maintain good health and improve the knowledge regarding pre conception care. The present study showed that structured teaching program was effective in improving knowledge among married women. The present study was conducted to enhance the structured teaching program among married women to improve knowledge regarding pre conception care. An experimental approach was adopted to conduct the present study. The sample was 60 married women (30 in experimental group and 30 in control group) and who were selected using purposive sampling technique from selected community Amritsar, Punjab.. The descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. The analysis findings of the study were depicted through the use of frequency distribution tables and bar diagrams and pie chart. It can be concluded that structured teaching program was effective in improving knowledge among married women regarding preconception care. So it was important to encourage the structured teaching program for improving knowledge regarding preconception care among married women to maintain health and to improve quality of life.

Limitation of the Study

1. The sample size of the study was small i.e.60 married women. Hence it is difficult to make generalization
2. Purposive sampling was done which restrict the generalization of findings
3. The study was limited to the married women residing in selected community in Punjab

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